

Heat Contents of Carbon Fuel Prepared from Rice Husk of Bago Region

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Abstract

The present research deals with the investigation of heat contents in carbon fuel from rice husk, the agricultural by-product from Kawa, Bago, Daik U and Painza Loke in Bago Region. Carbon fuel is daily used in energy fuel needs. Elemental contents in these samples were determined by using the EDXRF spectrometer. Differential thermal analysis was also performed by using DTG-60H in the different locations of Bago area in Myanmar. Heat contents of carbon fuel from Kawa, Bago, Daik U and Painza Loke were found to be 89.53, 115.67, 125.07 and 93.23 μV . It was observed that the heat contents in carbon fuel of Daik U area is most abundant (125 μV). The environmental contaminated Sulphur content is low percentage level at this Daik U area. This fuel cake showed that the improved properties with regard to energy emitted pattern when compared to the other preparative samples of different locations.

Keywords : Carbon fuel, heat content, sulphur content, DTG analysis , EDXRF analysis

Introduction

Carbon fuel prepared from other resources is quite varied from crop wastes. Using the rice husk to produce carbon fuel is significantly cheaper than other energies, such as non-renewable resources. The carbon fuel from rice husk is a valuable renewable resource and it has low pollution for our environment (Aksoy, 2006). The rice husk, also called rice hull, is the coating on a seed or grain of rice. It is formed from hard materials, including silica and lignin, to protect the seed during the growing season. Each kilogram of milled white rice results in roughly 0.28 kg of rice husk as a by-product of rice production during rice milling (Beagle, 1978). In the future, the global rice husk ash market is likely to benefit from many commercial opportunities at the back of its potential.

(a) Rice plant

(b) Rice husk

Figure: 1. Photograph of agricultural waste products:

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Thermal processes including combustion, gasification and pyrolysis were applied for rice husk after purified treatment. Energy products from rice husks were heat, electricity, and biofuels. Heat generated from this would be used for house heating and cooking, industrial boilers, drying, and generating electricity (Jenkins, 1998). Rice husk consists of a large amount of carbon in the composition of the natural polymer cellulose and lignin.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Sample

In this research, Rice husk samples were collected from Painza Loke, Daik U, Bago and Ka Wa from Bago Region, Myanmar. The collected samples were washed with water to remove impurities. They were dried at room temperature to prevent some reactions of the organic constituents present in samples with sun light. The four preparative samples were carbonized in the absence of air in a steel pipe at a temperature of 250 °C for 160 minutes. Carbonized rice husk is produced by thermal decomposition of the rice husk under a limited supply of oxygen.

Preparation of Carbon Fuel

The carbonized rice husk samples were mixed with starch paste, as binding agent, at the mixing ratio of 9:2. The agitating process was conducted in a mixer until the required condition for preparation of moulding was reached. The dense carbon fuel cake samples obtained were finally dried at room temperature.

Elemental Analysis by Using EDXRF Technique

In this research work, the rice husk carbon fuel cake samples were determined as metals in the various sites of Bago region, Myanmar. Relative abundance of elements present in the rice husk carbon fuel cake were determined by EDXRF spectrophotometer.

Measurement for Differential Thermal Gravimetric Technique

Carbon fuel cake of about 4 mg was accurately weighed into solid aluminium pans with sealed by using as a crimper (Type: SSC-30). The measurements were carried out at heating rate of 10 °C per minutes, under nitrogen atmosphere of 50 mL per minutes and scanning temperature ranged from 40 °C to 600 °C.

Results and Discussion

Relative Abundance of Elemental Content in the Various Carbon Fuel Cake

In this research work, the preparative carbon fuel cake were determined as metals in the different sites of Bago region, Myanmar. The percentage level of Si, K, Ca, Fe, Mn, Zn and S was found in various carbon fuel cake as shown in Table 1. In these results of Sulphur element, low level contents were examined in Painza Loke and Daik U.

Table 1: Relative Elemental Contents in the Various Carbon Fuel Samples by using EDXRF Technique

No	Sample Place	Relative Abundance (%)						
		Si	K	Ca	Fe	Mn	Zn	S
1.	Ka Wa	89.485	5.016	2.331	0.789	0.674	0.043	1.456
2.	Bago	-	41.931	19.938	8.575	15.218	1.306	9.521
3.	Daik U	77.743	8.633	9.095	1.811	0.570	0.042	1.396
4.	Painza Loke	93.399	4.124	1.336	0.361	0.693	0.031	-

Differential Thermalgravimetric Analysis

In this research, Figure: 2 to 5 shows the characteristics of TG-DTA thermograms. The Thermogram provided to evidence of marked features regarding the thermal stability of the prepared carbon fuel cake as shown in Tables 2 to 5. According to the TG-DTA thermogram profiles, prepared rice husk showed that the various heat contents.

Figure 2. TG-DTA thermogram of carbon fuel cake from Kawa

Figure 3. TG-DTA thermogram of carbon fuel cake from Bago

Table 2: Thermal Analysis Data for Carbon Fuel Cake from KaWa by using DTG-60H

Temp. Range (°C)	Break in Temp. (°C)	DTA Remark
40 – 100	79 °C first on set temp.	Endothermic peak due to vaporization (40.65 μV)
100 – 250	218 °C second on set temp.	Stable peak due to burnt Board-I (5.53 μV)
250 – 400	360 °C third on set temp.	Exothermic peak due to Carbonization (70.56 μV)
400 – 600	486 °C fourth on set temp.	Large Exothermic peak due to burnt (89.53 μV)

Table 3: Thermal Analysis Data for Carbon Fuel Cake from Bago by using DTG-60H

Temp. Range (°C)	Break in Temp. (°C)	DTA Remark
40 – 100	83 °C first on set temp.	Endothermic peak due to vaporization (31.42 μV)
100 – 250	211 °C second on set temp.	Stable peak due to burnt (3.22 μV)
250 – 400	366 °C third on set temp.	Exothermic peak due to Carbonization (89.77 μV)
400 – 600	479 °C fourth on set temp.	Large Exothermic peak due to burnt (115.67 μV)

Figure 4. TG-DTA thermogram of carbon fuel cake from Daik U

Figure 5. TG-DTA thermogram of carbon fuel cake from Painza Loke

Table 4: Thermal Analysis Data for Carbon Fuel Cake from Daik U by using DTG-60H

Temp. Range (°C)	Break in Temp. (°C)	DTA Remark
40 – 100	89 °C first on set temp.	Endothermic peak due to vaporization (50.83 μ V)
100 – 250	202 °C second on set temp.	Stable peak due to burnt (3.12 μ V)
250 – 400	337 °C third on set temp.	Exothermic peak due to Carbonization (90.97 μ V)
400 – 600	432 °C fourth on set temp.	Large Exothermic peak due to burnt (125.07 μ V)

Table 5: Thermal Analysis Data for Carbon Fuel Cake from Painza Loke by using DTG-60H

Temp. Range (°C)	Break in Temp. (°C)	DTA Remark
40 – 100	79 °C first on set temp.	Endothermic peak due to vaporization (25.15 μ V)
100 – 250	235 °C second on set temp.	Stable peak due to burnt (2.03 μ V)
250 – 400	362 °C third on set temp.	Exothermic peak due to Carbonization (40.27 μ V)
400 – 600	491 °C fourth on set temp.	Large Exothermic peak due to burnt (93.23 μ V)

Conclusion

Rice Husk samples were collected from Bago Region. The samples were carbonized in the absence of air in a furnace at a temperature of 250 °C for 160 mins. The concentration in percentage level of Si, K, Ca, Fe, Mn, Zn and S in various carbonized fuel were found. Sulphur contents of these fuel were found to be 1.456 %, 9.521 % and 1.396 % in preparative fuel cake from Kawa, Bago and Daik U respectively. From the result data, it was found that sulphur was not contained in carbon fuel cake from Painza Loke and low percentage level of sulphur was found in the Daik U sample (1.396 %). Heat contents of carbon fuel were found to be 89.53, 115.67, 125.07, 93.23, and 79.13 μ V in prepared fuel cake from Kawa, Bago, Daik U and Painza Loke respectively. Heat content in carbon fuel of Daik U and Painza Loke area were most abundant (125 μ V) and (115.67 μ V). As a result, It is good for our environment because of less pollution. It was also found that Daik U and Painza Loke samples were good for high energy production and Less pollution.

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